

Comparative Relationship between Leadership Role and Job Satisfaction among Senior Public Secondary School Teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined comparative relationship between leadership role and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. Two research questions and two corresponding hypotheses were framed to guide the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of 3,360 teachers (male, 2,062 and female, 1,298) during the 2016/2017 academic session in FCT, Abuja. A total of 360 teachers (male, 206 and female, 130) were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researcher. The questionnaire was validated and a logical validity index of 0.71 was obtained. The questionnaire was also pilot tested and yielded 0.87 reliability coefficient. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The findings revealed that, there is a significant relationship between leadership role and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Based on the findings, it was concluded that, there is significant relationship between leadership role of provision of instructional materials and maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. It was recommended that, management of FCT Secondary Education should provide enough funds to enable school principals provide instructional materials and maintain school facilities for job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Keywords: Relationship, Leadership role, teachers and job satisfaction

Introduction

Secondary education does not only occupy an important place in the Nigeria education system; it also serves as a link between the primary and tertiary levels. The Federal Republic of Nigeria in National Policy on Education, (2004) defined secondary education as the education a learner receives after primary education and before the tertiary stage. Secondary education prepares the individual for useful living within the society as well as the pivot on which the pursuit of higher education is built. Considering its importance, members of the public, therefore, places much importance to its development and hold high expectation of this level of education.

The head of secondary school leadership in Nigeria is the principal, who administers the school with other teaching and non-teaching staff. Accordingly, the principal is regarded as the chief executive of the school, who is responsible for all that, happens in the school. He or she is the accounting officer of the school and his position in the school is so germane to the extent that, the school cannot exist without that position (Babayemi, 2021). The principal is expected to provide leadership by performing certain roles as legally defined targeted at achieving efficient teaching and learning in the school.

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These roles according to Igwe (2018) among others include, provision of adequate instructional materials and resources, maintenance of school facilities, assigning teaching load and other responsibilities to teachers, communication with teachers on job expectations, and supervision of teaching and learning activities,

Principal is expected to perform his leadership roles by providing adequate instructional materials and resources for effective teaching and learning, reward and provides incentives for teachers who are outstanding in the discharge of their duties, carryout regular supervision of teaching and learning activities to ensure that the right teaching method, relevant materials and content are used (Igwe, 2018). Igwe, (2018) further stated that, he or she is equally expected to maintain school facilities to create conducive environment for both teachers and students to be able to teach and learn adequately and effectively, assign teaching load and other responsibilities to teachers with the skill and training to do them. More so, the principal is to communicate regularly with teachers on job expectations to ensure that teachers are adequately informed of what is expected of them and work enthusiastically towards goals attainment. These according to Ogunsanju (2022) will boost teacher's morale and ensure effective teaching and learning. Igwe, (2018) summed it up that principal performing his leadership roles will ensure teachers perform their jobs effectively for the smooth running of the school and the realization of educational goals as well as ensure teachers' job satisfaction.

Since leadership is an interactive relationship between leaders and followers, which is characterized by influence and identification according to Nwankwo (2019), the principal needs the co-operation of the teacher who is the key facilitator for the realization of educational goals. The teacher according to Ukeje (2018) is a professional, who in a morally accepted manner imparts knowledge and learning experiences at his disposal to stimulate, guide, direct and facilitate learners to acquire adequate mastery of the skills being imparted. Ukeje (2018) defined a teacher as someone who causes learning to take place, someone who imparts knowledge, skills, values and attitudes. Section 8 (6) of the national policy on education (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2004), stated that, no educational system may rise above the quality of its teachers. The teacher is therefore an important factor in the quality of education and the realization of educational goals in any nation including Nigeria. For quality service delivery to be achieved in any endeavour, job satisfaction of employee is a key component (Spector, 2010). Accordingly, for the teacher to provide quality education required for the ultimate advancement of the society, his job satisfaction should be guaranteed.

The impact of teachers' job satisfaction is very crucial to the long term growth of any educational system around the world. Man tends to render certain services if he is reasonably satisfied in his chosen career. Job satisfaction is desired in virtually all human organizations such as family, church, industry, civil service and the school for the purpose of attaining their stated objectives. Fafunwa in Popoola (2023), noted that both boys and girls in the traditional education settings performed their best in the art of hunting, farming and cooking when their morale were boosted by their parents through praises, incentives and other forms of motivation. However, those who excelled in the discharge of their duties or functions were normally praised and guided for better performance in future while those who performed below expectation were cautioned, assisted and guided for a good performance in future. The efficiency of any school system depends to a large extent upon how effectively human resources are utilized.

Locke (1986) in Popoola (2023), observed that job satisfaction refers to the pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job experience. Eneasator (1990) in Emaikwu, (2018), defined job satisfaction as the totality of an individual's psychological, social and physical well-being with regard to his work and job performance Teachers need to enjoy positive job satisfaction in order to be more functional and contribute meaningfully to the teaching and learning process in the school. In the context of this study, job satisfaction connotes teachers' pleasurable or positive and emotional state resulting from their job experiences in terms of availability of teaching and learning materials, supervision of teaching and learning activities, functional school facilities among others as provided by the principal to make teaching and learning condition very conducive for the teachers and students as well. Komolafe, (2020) stressed that if teachers lack job satisfaction their physiological needs will rarely be met and this will negatively influence their productive capacity, but if teachers enjoy job satisfaction, they tend to exhibit unprecedented love to their students through adequate teaching and research. Oluremi, (2019), observed that falling standard of education in Nigeria could be attributed to lack of job satisfaction among practicing teachers. He noted that the deplorable condition of teachers, is likened their low moral which invariably affects teaching and learning. Ogunsanju (2022) reported that the public is worried over this lack of job satisfaction among practicing teachers in the secondary school system in Nigeria. This according to him placed the government in Nigeria and union of teachers (NUT) in constant face – off over lack of job satisfaction resulting in the incessant strike action embarked by the teachers in primary

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and secondary schools in Nigeria. This ugly trend in the school system is evidently shown in the frequent work stop and long closure of schools resulting in truncated academic calendar and the complete breakdown of discipline, learning and scholarship. Fagbemi in Popoola (2023) noted that these days, teachers are found outside their school premises and even within the school premises, selling goods to the detriment of their duties. Part of the reasons for these actions of the teachers could be absence of job satisfaction among secondary school teachers.

However, it is widely believed in Nigeria that, teacher's job satisfaction is directly related to teachers' salary that is the quality of teachers' take-home pay. As a result of this, the Federal Government had made frantic efforts in the past to improve the quality of teachers' take-home pay. The most recent is the 27.5 percent increase in salary of teachers in public schools in Nigeria in line with the new teachers salary scale through the Governor's forum in 2009 (Komolafe, 2020). In addition, the Federal Capital Territory administration in 2005 approved special allowances for teachers posted to the rural areas, science teachers and a 100 percent payment of housing allowance in advance annually (federal capital secondary schools education board 2022). Again, the president of the National Union of Teachers (NUT) when making suggestions on how to improve the educational system, in Nigeria, said, "Government must develop a remuneration and reward system that will promote job satisfaction of teachers" (Komolafe, 2020). Despite the effort by the government teachers' still exhibit lack of enthusiasm and commitment for the job, absenteeism, truancy and engaging in petty trading within and outside the school, above all leave the profession suddenly in search of greener pastures. (Huberman, 2023) This according to Huberman (2023) may affect the quality of teachers in schools and students' academic performance in both internal and external examinations (SSCE, WAEC NECO and JAMB).

More so, in recent times, principals of secondary schools in Nigeria have been accused by stakeholders in the education sector (parent, teachers, students etc) of failing to provide effective and adequate leadership role for their schools. They are said to be inefficient in performing their leadership roles practices and accused of various lapses and offenses that result in teachers not deriving satisfaction with their job (Dubi 2018). Also, the instructive competence of the school principal is the engine that motivates teacher's performance and job satisfaction, but most principals are not effective in their leadership behaviour, they treat teachers as tools believing that teachers can be treated anyhow; their query to them after a minor mistake; they do not recommend them for promotion as at when due; don't reward teachers and provide incentives to motivate them; they supervised teachers only to find fault without providing useful advice, fails to communicate with teachers on job expectations regularly and so on. In addition, Government at all levels have been accused of concentrating more on improving the quality of teachers' take home pay without doing much on other areas that may have impact on teachers' welfare. All these according to Bussing, (2019) may have significant effect on teachers attitude to work and job satisfaction. These issues have been a source of concern to this researcher to go into this area to unravel whether principals' leadership roles practices have any significant influence on teachers' job satisfaction in public senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

Over the years the government both at Federal and State level had put in more efforts in the past to improve the quality of teachers' take-home pay (salary) with the believed that in Nigeria, teacher's job satisfaction is directly related to teachers' salary, which is the quality of teachers' take-home pay. The most recent is the 27.5 percent increase in salary of teachers in public schools in Nigeria in line with the new teachers salary scale through the Governor's forum in 2010. Also, the Federal Capital Territory administration in effort to improve the welfare of its' teachers in 2018 approved special allowances for teachers posted to the rural areas, science teachers and a 100 percent payment of housing allowance in advance annually (federal capital secondary schools education board 2018). In spite of this teacher's still exhibit lack of enthusiasm and commitment for the job, they exhibit absenteeism, truancy and engaging in petty trade within and outside the school during school hour and above all leaving the profession suddenly in search of greener pastures. All these attitudes may be a clear demonstration of lack of job satisfaction among teachers in Nigeria in general and Federal Capital Territory in particular. This lack of job satisfaction among teachers despite improvement in their take home pay (salaries) may have been attributed to poor leadership role performance by school administrators (Principals) in providing good and conducive working environment particularly leadership role of providing adequate instructional materials and maintenance of school facilities for effective teaching and learning. In recent times, principals of secondary schools in Nigeria particularly in FCT have been accused of failing to provide effective and adequate leadership role for their schools. That they are said to be inefficient in performing their leadership role and accused of various lapses in the discharge of their duties. They fail to provide adequate and relevant instructional materials to enable teachers teach their lessons with ease and maintain school facilities to provide teachers with conducive classrooms and furniture for both teachers and students, comfortable office accommodation etc It is in lieu of the above premise that the

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study sought to determine whether besides salary there is significant relationship between leadership role and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory.

Objectives of the study:

The main objective of the study was to determine the comparative relationship between leadership roles and job satisfaction among secondary schools teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfactions among secondary schools teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.
2. The relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among secondary schools teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Research Questions:

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

1. What is the relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary School teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary School teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design and the type of survey design was correlational design. According to Emaikwu (2018) correlational research design attempt to established relationship between two or more variables. The design is suitable for this study as the study sought to establish or determine the relationship between leadership role and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. Population of the study consists of 3,360 teachers (male, 2,062 and female, 1,298) during the 2016/2017 academic session drawn from all the 59 public senior secondary schools in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. A total of 360 teachers (male, 206 and female, 130) were sampled from the target population using simple random sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was a questionnaire developed by the researcher titled Relationship between Leadership Role and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (RLRJS) was used for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by experts in the Department of Educational Management and Test and Measurement from the Faculty of Education, Nasarawa State University, Keffi. This enabled the researcher to obtained logical validity index of 0.71 and the value so obtained was considered sufficient to use the instrument. The questionnaire was pilot tested using 50 teachers from two (2) schools that were part of the population but not part of the sampled population. The data collected was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha correlation co-efficient which yielded 0.87. The coefficient indicated high internal consistency which proved that the instrument was reliable for the study. A total of 360 questionnaires were administered, 336 were filled and returned representing 86% return rate. The data collected was analyzed using simple descriptive statistic of mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. A mean cut-off point of 2.50 was used for decision. The research hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria?

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Table 1: Mean and standard deviation showing the relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria **Scale = 2.5**

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Instructional materials	3.07	1.87	High
2	Low relationship	2.98	1.77	High
	Aggregate	3.03	1.82	High

Field work

Table 1 shows the aggregate mean of 3.03 and standard deviation of 1.82 is above the scale mean of 2.50. The result from the analysis shows that, the relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction is high among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation showing the relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among senior public secondary school teachers in federal capital territory, Abuja Nigeria. **Scale = 2.5**

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Maintenance of school facilities	3.09	1.87	High
2	Job satisfaction	3.17	1.87	High
	Aggregate	3.13	1.87	High

Field work

Table 2 shows the aggregate mean of 3.13 and standard deviation of 1.87 is above the scale mean of 2.50. The result from the analysis shows that, the relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction is high among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Testing of the hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between availability of instructional materials job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Table 3: Correlation Coefficient showing relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in federal capital territory, Abuja Nigeria

S/N	Variable	Correlation Coefficient(r)	Level of Significance (0.05)
1.	Availability of instructional materials		
2.	Job satisfaction among Teachers	0.70	Significant

df= 334 $\alpha = 0.05$,

Table 3 shows the result of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r) analysis of availability of instructional materials and its relationship with job satisfaction among teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. The calculated r is 0.70 and is found to be significantly high when compared with the table value of 0.05 at degree of freedom. Since the calculated value is higher than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected, indicating that there is significant relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria

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Table 4: Correlation Coefficient showing relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in federal capital territory, Abuja Nigeria

S/N	Variable	Correlation Coefficient(r)	Level of Significance (0.05)
1.	Maintenance of school facilities		
2.	Job satisfaction among Teachers	0.80	Significant

df= 334 $\alpha = 0.05$.

Table 4 shows the result of Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r) analysis of maintenance of school facilities and its relationship with job satisfaction among teachers. The calculated r is 0.80 and is found to be significantly high when compared with the table value of 0.05 at degree of freedom. Since the calculated value is higher than the table value, the null hypothesis is therefore rejected, indicating that there is significant relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary schools teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. This follows that availability of instructional materials gives job satisfaction to teachers. The above finding corroborates with the view of Alio and Ezeamaeyi (2019) who stated that, availability of instructional materials not only support and reinforces teaching, also provides the teacher with interesting compelling platforms for conveying information since they motivate learners to learn more and that, when the students are given the chance to learn through more senses than one, they can learn faster and easier. According to them, when the students learn faster and easier the teacher feels satisfied. Alio and Ezeamaeyi (2019) went further to elaborate that, availability of instructional materials assist teachers in overcoming physical difficulties that could have hindered their effective presentation of a given topic and a shift from teacher to student-centered classes. This according to them removes stress from the teachers and that teachers whose work is not stressful derived some level of satisfaction and fulfillment in their jobs.

Again, it was discovered that there exist a strong positive correlation between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among teachers in the study area. This means that, school facilities, has a strong relationship with job satisfaction, by implication; it is evident that job satisfaction among teachers depends to a large extent on good and functional school facilities. It is important to note that teachers and indeed their students need conducive environment to be able to teach and learn adequately and effectively. The above finding correlates with the opinion of Ntukidem (2022) who submitted that, since man loves beauty and becomes relaxed and comfortable within a beautiful environment, it is therefore imperative that school principal should endeavour to put the existing structures into proper function by either renovating or do regular repairs to meet with expected standards. He further maintains that attractive school plants with superior lighting, attractive decoration, comfortable seating and useful service facilities such as libraries, multi-purpose room give teachers a sense of belonging, fulfillment and satisfaction. Supporting the opinion of Ntukidem (2022) National Clearinghouse for Educational Facilities, (2023) stated that, teachers want to work in quality facilities and have access to appropriate and needed materials and resources. An important factor in the employment decisions made by individual teachers is the quality of school facilities, that poor school conditions increase the likelihood that teachers will leave that school and even the teaching profession. North Carolina State Board of Education, (2019) is in agreement that, teachers must have working conditions that allow them to do their jobs, and facilities must be designed, well-maintained, and utilized to support job satisfaction. Teachers who leave their teaching assignment cite opportunities for a better teaching assignment, professional development, leadership, empowerment, and facilities and resources and dissatisfaction with workplace conditions as the main reasons they seek additional employment.

Conclusion

In view of the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn: that there is significant relationship between availability of instructional materials and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal

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Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria. The study further reveals that there is significant relationship between maintenance of school facilities and job satisfaction among public senior secondary school teachers in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of Federal Capital Territory Secondary Education Board and other stakeholders should provide enough Funds for the provision of adequate instructional materials to enable teachers perform their duties effectively to give them Job satisfaction.
2. The management of Federal Capital Territory Secondary Education Board and other stakeholders should provide enough Funds for the maintenance of school facilities to give teachers a comfortable environment to carry out their duties and have Job satisfaction.

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